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RURAL TOURISM: DEVELOPMENT OPPORTUNITIES IN MODERN RUSSIA

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Abstract. The article considers the possibilities and prospects of rural tourism development in modern Russia, emphasises the importance of the existence of this sector in the general concept of tourism development. The author defines the concepts of rural and agrotourism, specifies the types of rural tourism in the proposed classification. The history of emergence goes back to Antiquity, in Russia the first manifestations are noted in the XVII century and a leap in development occurs in the XIX century. In connection with the current economic situation and the situation in the Russian market of countryside real estate, there are clear prerequisites for the development of this sector, there is an increase in demand for recreation in the countryside. Among the main advantages of rural tourism for consumers are small financial costs, convenient location not far from cities, the opportunity to study the history of the region, customs, traditions, a wide target audience (any age, interests, employment, social status of potential tourists), participation in agricultural work. In modern conditions and with the support of the state there is an opportunity to create micro and small businesses in Russia. The stages of creation and implementation of a startup in the rural tourism sector are: development of a unique idea, confirmation, launching the business, the stage of growth and development and the stage of scaling. With a properly chosen strategy and adherence to the development algorithm, the creation and launch of a startup seems realistic.

Keywords: rural tourism, agrotourism, rural areas, farming, development strategies, startup

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СЕЛЬСКИЙ ТУРИЗМ. ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ РОССИИ

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются возможности и перспективы развития сельского туризма в современной России, подчеркивается важность существования данного сектора в общей концепции развития туризма. Автором даются определения понятий «сельский» и «агротуризм», указываются виды сельского туризма в предложенной классификации. История возникновения уходит корнями в Античность, в России первые проявления отмечаются в XVII веке и скачок в развитии происходит в XIX веке. В связи с текущей экономической ситуацией и обстановкой на российском рынке загородной недвижимости существуют явные предпосылки развития данного сектора, отмечен рост спроса на отдых за городом. Среди основных преимуществ сельского туризма для потребителей выделяются небольшие финансовые затраты, удобное расположение недалеко от городов, возможность изучать историю края, обычаи, традиции, широкая целевая аудитория (любой возраст, интересы, занятость, социальное положение потенциальных туристов), участие в сельскохозяйственных работах. В современных условиях и при поддержке государства существует возможность создания микро- и малого бизнеса в России. Этапами создания и реализации стартапа в секторе сельского туризма являются: разработка уникальной идеи, подтверждение, запуск бизнеса, этап роста и развития и этап масштабирования. При правильно выбранной стратегии и соблюдении алгоритма развития создание и запуск стартапа представляется реальным.

Ключевые слова: сельский туризм, агротуризм, сельская местность, фермерство, стратегии развития, стартап

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In the modern world, the tourism industry is one of the fastest growing sectors of the economy. According to the assessments of specialists of the World Bank Institute, tourism today ranks second in the world economy after mechanical engineering in terms of sales volumes, and among other service industries, it takes the leading place. Also, the total economic contribution of tourism was 3.3 trillion dollars last year, or three per cent of global GDP, providing more than 320 million jobs worldwide (10 million jobs in Russia).

One of the most promising sectors in the field of tourism is rural tourism, contributing to the active attraction of new investments both in specific tourist facilities and in the direct development of agricultural production. It should be noted the possibility of providing significant support for the life of local residents in the form of income from the provision of services and the sale of agricultural products, which, in turn, if the process is properly organised, can significantly reduce the outflow of young residents from rural areas, as well as significantly improve the standard of living of local residents and increase the volume of food production. [8, pp. 59–73, 9, pp. 23–29]

Note that it is worth separating such related concepts as rural tourism and agro-tourism. Rural tourism is a more general term, which implies a system of associations of production and social sphere of agriculture and tourism, united to maximise profits and solve social problems. Rural tourism includes recreation outside the city, getting acquainted with local colour, national values, customs, traditions. Agrotourism, however, includes leisure activities that are offered directly by farmers to serve visitors, which in most cases is a source of additional income for farmers in addition to the main employment. [3, p. 77–79] Agritourism is understood as a type of recreation in rural areas with participation in the activities of an agricultural enterprise.

In the presented classification of rural tourism the following types are distinguished:

- agricultural tourism (harvesting, caring for animals and poultry on the farm, cultivating the land, planting crops, weeding, watering and other work in the farm – tourists can not only observe the process but also directly participate in it);
- children's tourism (for families with children, as well as for organised children's groups – from orphanages, summer children's camps, schools, kindergartens – assumes the availability of equipment for children – inventory, playgrounds);

- stay tourism ('to live in the village' – renting a house, summer cottage, country cottage);
- cognitive (excursions to study the sights of the area, observation of animals, birds, plants);
- exotic (watching the cultivation of unusual animals – ostriches, minks, caesars, alpacas, as well as exotic plants);
- adventurous (may include hiking, rafting on rivers and lakes, combining stops in tents and village houses);
- sports (active sports – horse riding, cycling, hiking, canoeing, skiing, skating in winter);
- practical experience tourism (gaining life experience, which can often be used in work on psychological correction in difficult life situations);
- gastronomic tours (traditional dishes and drinks, peculiarities and details of preparation);
- community ecotourism (eco-community tourism);
- ethnographic tourism (acquaintance with local customs and traditions, optional participation in festivals, organization of museums of folk life, folklore groups may be invited);
- combined (combines several directions of recreation). [4, p. 19–20]

The history of rural tourism dates back to the times of Antiquity, when ancient pilgrims set off on long journeys to distant countries to learn more about their culture, traditions, customs, manners, everyday life, habits, etc., and on their return they shared their fascinating stories with the locals. Scientists-historians know the fact that in the VI century BC ancient Romans travelled to Egypt to see the Nile, its floods, pyramids, to get acquainted with the original Eastern culture, life away from the familiar places. The ancient Greek philosopher Democritus of Abdera (c. 460 B.C.) argued that it is possible to know nature only through direct contact with it. During the Renaissance, the best minds of mankind, such as Michel de Montaigne, Thomas More, pointed out the special role of long walks on the development of human personality. During the Middle Ages in Italy and other European countries there were schools in which students were taught special skills of tourism, carrying out hiking trips to the Alps. [6, p. 113]

In Russia, the origins of rural tourism go back to the XVII century, when the capital centres emerged, and in the north-western part of the country, lands located in the territories of the present-day Leningrad, Novgorod, Pskov regions and the Republic of Karelia were allocated for the use of the court nobility. During the reign of Anna

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loannovna, when a middle class of merchants, civil servants, and teachers of educational institutions was formed in Russia, it turned out that this class did not get the lands allocated for ownership, and, therefore, the representatives of this class used the practice of going to the countryside for family holidays. Also, as a result of the construction of the St. Petersburg-Varshavskaya and Nikolaevskaya railways in the second half of the 19th century, rural areas were massively built up with summer houses and spacious estates, including those for rent, which gave rise to rural tourism in Russia. Gatchina, Oredezh, Razliv, Lisiy Nos, Lakhta and Sestroretsk were considered the most popular dacha areas. It was at this time that the so-called 'dacha trade' emerged in tsarist Russia, which was the prototype of the dacha business as part of rural tourism. The townspeople, who tended to go out of town in the hot season, brought substantial income to local landlords, intermediaries, as well as the local population, buying their agricultural products. [1, pp. 93–94] During the difficult period of the early 20th century, during the First and then the Second World Wars, rural tourism was less popular for obvious reasons. However, throughout the Soviet period one of the most popular types of holidays was dacha tourism. Only in the 1990s rural tourism entered a new and very promising stage of its development. According to the Concept of long-term socio-economic development of the Russian Federation 'Strategy–2020, new growth model – new social policy', one of the most important conditions for the transition of the Russian economy to a socially-oriented type of management is the creation of conditions for improving the quality of human life, including through the development of tourism industry infrastructure, ensuring the quality, accessibility and competitiveness of national tourism services. Obviously, the emphasis is placed on the development of specifically Russian tourism product, and rural tourism in particular as one of the promising sectors. [6, p.119]

In addition, the factors that were certain triggers for the development of rural tourism in Russia were the pandemic that began in March 2020, as well as the economic and political situation, due to which Russians were no longer able to travel abroad in the same volume as they did in the period of the noughties and tens of the XXI century, when outbound tourism reached its greatest popularity. Accordingly, people have actively rushed to the countryside, clearly recognising the clear advantages of renting (both long-term and short-term) or owning a country property.

As a result of the research conducted by Domklik in August 2024 on the country property market in some districts of the Moscow region, there is a significant increase in the cost of long-term rental of country property (on average by 22,9 %) for the past year (July 2023 – July 2024), as well as a clear decline in supply (on average by 40,8 %), which proves the strong growth in demand for real estate near Moscow. Accordingly, we can conclude that people tend to spend more time away from the hustle and bustle of the city, enjoying nature (Table 1).

In addition, we can observe an even more pronounced tendency for the price of daily rent of countryside property to rise not only in the Moscow region, but also in the country as a whole. For the year from winter 2022–2023 to winter 2023–2024, the average cost of daily rent of country property in Russia has risen by 17 %, according to information provided by the press service of the Avito Real Estate platform. Prices have increased in such regions participating in the research as Buryatia (by 60 %), Adygea (by 50 %), Bashkortostan (by 40 %), Kursk and Penza regions, Karachay-Cherkessia. It is interesting to note that this dynamics can be observed against the background of growth in the number of facilities for daily accommodation of travellers. In the segment of suburban housing

Table 1. Analysis of the long-term rental market of country houses in the Moscow region (August 2024).

Settlement point	Change in the volume of supply over the past year	Cost of renting a house with the area of 100 sq. m, thousand rubles/month	Change in rental cost over the past year, %
Odintsovo	-53,2 %	113	+4,3 %
Istra	-53,4 %	127,3	+12,8 %
Krasnogorsk	-33,3 %	138,5	+33,2 %
Ramenskoye	-25 %	60	+20,0 %
Mytishchi	-39,3 %	73,1	+44,1 %

in 13 regions at once the supply for one year has grown 2 or more times. All these factors prove the existence of a huge demand for countryside accommodation, time spent away from the bustle of the city, and, accordingly, clear prerequisites for the development of domestic rural tourism in Russia.

Rural tourism in Western European countries is the second most popular after beach tourism and generates more than 30 % of the total income of the tourism industry. There are specially created structures to promote rural tourism, which encourage its development at the national level, for example, the European Federation of Rural Green Tourism EUROGITIS, uniting 20 associations from 17 European countries. Italy, Spain, Germany are leaders in this sector and have more pronounced traditions in organising leisure activities for tourists outside major cities. The Czech Republic, Poland, Slovakia and Austria are actively increasing their capacities to receive rural tourists.

In Russia, the current state of rural tourism is rather modest. So far, this type of tourism accounts for only 1 % of the domestic tourist flow. However, there are real steps in this direction. In July 2021, the President of the Russian Federation signed the law 'On the foundations of tourism activity in the Russian Federation', which introduces the concept of 'rural tourism'. Some regions are actively developing this direction. Leaders in the organisation of rural tourism are the Vologda, Leningrad, Ivanovo, Vladimir, Penza, Tver, Samara, Yaroslavl, Tula, Novgorod, Arkhangelsk regions, Moscow Region, Krasnodar Krai, Karelia, Chuvashia, Buryatia, Altai Krai Tatarstan. [7] Long-term target programmes and projects are being developed and implemented in these regions.

According to the research conducted by analysts of the consulting company 'ATLAS Bureau', such potentially attractive regions as Siberia (Altai, Tyva, Khakassia), North Caucasus (North Ossetia-Alania and Dagestan), Lower Volga region, where Saratov, Volgograd and Astrakhan regions can become an integral cluster, are among the most promising areas for the development of this type of tourism.¹

In 2013, an organisational structure was established in the Russian Federation – the National Association of Rural and Ecotourism, the purpose of which is to form a strong community of like-minded people for the development and promotion of rural, ecological and

related types of tourism. The tasks of this organisation are to unite individuals and legal entities working in this area in different regions of the country, to develop a convenient platform for professional communication and interaction, to establish strong business contacts with government agencies at the federal level and lobby the interests of practitioners of the sector, to reach the international level, interacting with foreign partners and adapting successful world experience for Russia. It is a membership organisation whose members can be legal entities and citizens who recognise the Association's Charter. On the basis of this structure there is the Academy of Rural Tourism, which conducts online lessons, webinars, organises study tours, develops and implements professional development programmes.²

However, given the size of the country and its population, this niche is extremely promising, especially in the current period of time, when there are still serious restrictions on direct flights to European countries, especially on the Mediterranean coast, which Russian travellers preferred to choose as their favourite destinations earlier. Not all tourists are ready to make connecting flights, 12-hour and longer air journeys, which not everyone can afford financially. Russians, however, are distinguished by a special love and affection for their country, marvellous nature and land. In addition, it is a well-known fact that often people living in a particular area simply do not have time to visit the places around them, which are close to their homes, either because they are busy or for some other reason. Currently, there is a growing demand for weekend tours (including bus tours) to destinations that are not too far from the places where tourists live.

Let's consider the advantages of rural tourism:

1. Low cost of travelling, as the facilities are mostly located close to cities.
2. Accessibility for the whole family. It can provide an excellent opportunity to spend free time – weekends, holidays together with children.
3. the lowest energy costs. Saving time and financial resources – there is no need to spend time and money on buying airline tickets, choosing and booking hotels, issuing visas, organising and paying for transfers.
4. A great opportunity to rest, seclude, relax and reboot in nature, away from noisy and densely populated metropolises with a very fast pace of life.

¹ <https://archsovet.msk.ru/news/v-atlas-nazvali-3-samyh-perspektivnyh-regiona-dlya-razvitiya-sel-skogo-turizma-v-rossii>

² <https://selturacademia.ru/akademiya/>

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5. It is interesting to get acquainted with the history of the region, traditions, customs, manners of people living in a completely different environment.

6. Studying the objects of cultural and national heritage located near the object of stay (museums, monasteries, nature reserves, eco-farms, equestrian clubs, etc.).

7. Due to its close proximity to major cities, the possibility of cooperation with medical institutions and social centres, hospices, specific assistance to people with diseases, disabled people (children and adults), people in difficult life situations – providing opportunities to stay in the fresh air, observation of agricultural processes and/or direct participation in them, communication with domestic animals, hippotherapy.

8. If you wish, you can take part in agricultural work – tilling the land, caring for plants and pets, planting and growing flowers, vegetable and fruit crops.

9. Participation in folk rituals – immersion in the atmosphere of rural life. Possibility of independent production of costumes and props for events.

10. Opportunity to go fishing, hunting, gathering mushrooms and berries.

11. Attend master classes on mastering the skills of crafts – pottery, blacksmithing, carpentry, embroidery, spinning, weaving.

12. Accessibility of this format of recreation and spending free time for almost any target audience – children, the elderly, children with special needs, the disabled.

13. Choice of any duration of recreation – from a half day to several months.

The study conducted by I.V. Lebedeva and S.L. Kopylova in 2019 highlights the following negative factors affecting pricing and the number of guests in the village:

1. Low quality of roads.
2. Insufficient promotion (advertising, marketing).
3. Weak infrastructure.
4. Lack of trained personnel.
5. Insufficient number of accommodation facilities.
6. Insufficient government support.
7. Insufficient level of service and quality of facilities.
8. Insufficient work with rural residents.
9. Fears among the local population. [5, с.12]

It is interesting to consider the possibilities of building a small business or start-up in the rural tourism sector. [7,

p. 109–116] These two concepts are different from each other. The distinctive feature of a startup is the presence of an absolutely unique idea, as well as rapid, rapid growth. Accordingly, small business is characterised by a smoother development in an already well-known niche. Other features of a startup are considered to be:

- complete absence of investments or minimal costs to launch the project;
- if the strategy is correctly chosen and successfully built, the startup can start to bring tangible profit rather quickly (in 0,5–2 years);
- rather high risk of failure;
- at the initial stage, a very small startup team – in some cases, only a few people united by a common idea will suffice;
- the main goals of the enterprise are to satisfy the needs of customers who could not do so earlier due to the lack of such a niche in the market or because of an unfilled niche, and not only to make profit;
- the need to attract additional sources of financing from interested investors.

There are 5 main stages of creating and implementing a startup.

1. Development of the main unique idea, which was previously completely absent on the market. Realisation of the idea should meet the condition – to close the existing needs of potential customers.

2. Pre-seed stage – validation. At this stage, feedback through social networks is carried out, as well as the search for potential investors.

3. Launch of the startup. Entering the market and observing the reaction and evaluation of the product by the target audience through social media interaction, media promotion and other means.

4. Growth and development stage – spreading in the market, capturing the chosen niche.

5. Scaling stage. The business grows and develops, options are considered for brand stretching and direct implementation of the programme in full, goals are achieved, short-term and long-term, interested investors are attracted and gradual entry into new markets is carried out.

As an example of the creation and further development of a startup in the studied sector of agrotourism, we can consider such an idea as the organisation of a guest house for leisure activities in the countryside near Moscow, located 30–40 kilometres from the metropolis. This location will reduce the time and financial costs for tourists to easily reach the destination. The site could

be based on unfinished buildings or farm buildings that are no longer used for their intended purpose for certain reasons, such as barns, cowsheds, storage facilities for agricultural machinery and/or equipment, etc. in order to reduce the cost of building from scratch, provided that these buildings can be converted into a cottage or guest house. At the initial stage it can be a room for a day's leisure, it does not matter, tourists choose just to relax in nature or to celebrate some event in the family circle or among friends – birthday, graduation party, anniversary. It is necessary to equip the premises in accordance with sanitary norms and to give a well-groomed appearance to the surrounding area, so that clients would be pleasant to be both indoors and outdoors.

At the endorsement stage, feedback is activated mainly through social networks, although alternative methods of interaction can be used both with the target audience and potential investors, whose attraction is also one of the main tasks of the second stage.

At the stage of product launch and market entry, we are talking about increasingly intensified feedback via social media and social networks. If marketing strategies are chosen and developed correctly, positive dynamics are most likely. It is at this point that it is important to consider various factors and take them into account. Particular attention should be paid to:

1. collection and processing of necessary information (correctly formulated questions, clearly structured communication before, during and after the guests' stay at the facility);
2. safety of both the object itself and the stay on its territory;
3. sustainability as a concept of business existence (energy-saving lighting, use of disposable plastic utensils, utilisation of household rubbish and other waste);
4. the possibility to book a stay not only by phone and from a computer, but also from a mobile device;
5. the possibility of contactless payment;
6. partnership with neighbouring objects of related business, as well as cultural and natural heritage (museums, manor houses, nature reserves, horse clubs, eco-farms);
7. flexible booking system (deferred payment and cancellation option);
8. video marketing (guests have the opportunity to watch short video clips about the property on the Internet, including video testimonials from clients who have been there).

If marketing promotion strategies are chosen and work correctly, the appropriate niche is captured and development takes place: that is, a guest house for a one-night stay has every chance of becoming a mini hotel. There are means and possibility to equip rooms for longer stay of guests – for two or three nights and more. Consequently, the tourist attraction becomes more attractive to potential guests.

Thus, this stage turns into the final stage and the business is scaled up. We can talk about stretching – organising various activities on the territory, such as a pottery workshop, sports and children's playgrounds, animation programmes – contests, discos, masquerades, games. Video and photo reports from these events serve as excellent content for social media promotion. If sufficient capacity is available and activated, it is possible to build and equip additional buildings on the same territory. In addition, co-operation with related businesses in the same region – organic farms, stables, equestrian clubs, etc. – is strengthened. As a result, the business is expanding and we can already talk about the emergence of a whole cluster consisting of several interacting companies that provide clients with a whole range of services from accommodation and organising events in the countryside to various activities and even cultural leisure (museums, holy places, museums-reserves).

It is worth noting that there is state support for farming and rural tourism. In 2022, 51 projects in this sector were selected for grants totalling 300 million roubles. In 2023, 500 million roubles were allocated for grants for farms. In 2024, this amount increased to 700 million roubles. The maximum amount of the grant 'Agrotourism' is 10 million roubles. Micro and small businesses registered in rural areas have the opportunity to receive the grant. The grant is allocated on the basis of competitive selection. Any agricultural producers recognised as such by the results of the previous year – joint stock companies, peasant farms, agricultural cooperatives, individual entrepreneurs – can take part in the competition. In addition to financial support, the state provides information support. Information about the facilities must be entered into the unified register of accommodation facilities. The facilities include camping sites, glamping sites, recreation centres, modular hotels.

On 22 June 2024, the Russian government issued a law on the basis of which farmers were allowed to accommodate tourists in guest houses located on agricultural land. This document gives the right to carry

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out activities in the sphere of rural tourism on land plots that have the status of agricultural land.

In the process of establishment and development of enterprises in the rural tourism sector, it is possible to build cooperation with educational institutions of this profile, for example, the Russian University of Tourism and Service, whose students can study not only rural tourism as such, but also observe and participate in the construction of business in this area, which expands the range of specialities that can be involved in the project. For example, not only students studying tourism and hotel management, but also students of the Higher School of Management and other economic specialities can undergo practical training at ready-made and under construction facilities. Thus, there is an opportunity to train personnel for the rural tourism sector. Furthermore, while working in such enterprises in teams and collaborating, students have a valuable chance to learn and train their soft skills, which is often even of more importance, than hard or professional skills. [2, pp. 41–50]

It is worth mentioning such a promising direction as attracting foreign tourists, more active entry into the international market, i.e., the development of inbound tourism. This will attract additional investments into the state budget. Also, in the context of international co-operation we can talk about new partnerships, exchange of experience, conclusion of new contracts in this interesting sphere. We should consider alternatives of collaboration between educational institutions in the tourism industry, student exchange programmes and internships abroad.

Based on the above factors, which prove the clear advantages of rural tourism development in quite a large number of geographical areas, we can conclude that with competent organisation, correctly chosen location and a clear structural approach to the establishment, launch and development of rural tourism facilities, the implementation of business in this promising sector in the Russian market has a very good chance of success.

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